

The Effect of Social Capital, Human Capital on Social Entrepreneurial Orientation among Undergraduate Students: Entrepreneurial Awareness as a Mediator

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Abstract

In contemporary times, social capital and human capital have become important topics for business practitioners and academics. Because the entrepreneurship environment has become more competitive, the need to develop and improve social capital and human capital has become crucial. Despite the importance of social capital and human capital, researches linking these concepts to the social entrepreneurial orientation of students are very limited. Through an extensive literature view, this study has found a theoretical link between social capital, human capital and social entrepreneurial orientation and also developed a conceptual model for empirical validations. This study serves not only to clarify the relationships among social capital, human capital, and social entrepreneurial orientation; it also helps to explain the role that entrepreneurial awareness plays as a mediator in this relationship, which most studies have neglected. Lastly, the study contributes to the debate about whether human capital or social capital is most vital for entrepreneurs

Keywords: social capital, human capital, social entrepreneurial orientation, and entrepreneurial awareness.

1. Introduction

Recent years have witnessed a remarkable increase in entrepreneurship research, practices and policies (Agarwal, Dushnitsky, Lumpkin, Wright, 2017; Levenburg & Schwarz, 2008), showing great breadth, depth and rigor (Sharma & Singh, 2017; Zahra & Wright, 2016). Entrepreneurship has been argued to be a key driver of any economy because of its significant impact through job creations, turning inventions into innovations and improving the overall welfare of the state. Indeed, entrepreneurs have launched new technologies that have created numerous industries and jobs and have bettered the economic and social conditions of several nations (Baumol, 2013; Dogan, 2015; McMullen & Warnick, 2015; Zahra & Wright, 2016).

In the literature, social entrepreneurship has become a key research domain and has continued to attract the attention of enormous scholars in many ways. Within the last three decades, social entrepreneurship has emerged as an active area of practice and research and has become increasingly important as an international cultural phenomenon (André & Pache, 2016; Dacin T., Dacin A. & Tracey, 2011; Kasemsap, 2017; Kraus, Filser, O'Dwyer & Shaw, 2014). Conceptually, social entrepreneurship is used as an umbrella term for people and organizations that aim to solve a societal problem using innovative solutions. In addition, social entrepreneurship is understood as the concept of social value creation, and scholars have argued that organizational forms should stay in the domain of non-profits (Mokhtar & Rahim, 2014; Rahim & Lajin, 2015; Rahim & Mohtar, 2015; Pirson, 2009; Pirson, 2012).

Social entrepreneurship has become progressively popular as a practice in which business solutions are used on social problems (Choi & Majumdar, 2014; Cunha & Benneworth, 2014). Over the last decade, social entrepreneurship has played a critical role in the development of many emerging economies (Bhandari, 2017; Hamid, Hengchao & Mhd-Sarif, 2017; Danowski, 2015). In studying the phenomenon of social entrepreneurship, case studies showcasing profiles of social enterprises and innovative entrepreneurs have been utilized (Nicolopoulou, 2014).

In Malaysia, the development of the concept of entrepreneurship and the creation of entrepreneurial activities are becoming more important. Indeed, a large number of supporting mechanisms and policies for entrepreneurs including business advisory services, funding, and physical infrastructures, and the establishment

of a special ministry for entrepreneurs has demonstrated the great value that policymakers have associated with entrepreneurship to the growth of Malaysian economy (Ministry of Entrepreneur Development Malaysia, 2019).

New social enterprise creation is a phenomenon that helps to drive the modern international marketplace. This type of creation is integral to the development of emerging projects, to the expansion of established industries within emerging economies, and ultimately, to the general economic growth (Mohamad et al., 2011; Rainwater, 2016; Taatila & Down, 2012). Innovation within new firms is a common occurrence, which, in turn, promotes industry-wide innovation, as rival organizations must also develop new products and adaptive marketing strategies to remain competitive (Alkier, Milojica & Roblek, 2017; Obschonka, Silbereisen & Schmitt-Rodermund, 2012). Undergraduate students are perceived to be the most suitable to be groomed as innovators and entrepreneurs, and an entrepreneurial orientation is an important catalyst for a lasting innovation orientation among students (Nordin, 2015).

In other parts of the world, knowledge, experience, ties, relationship configurations, personal values, beliefs and attitudes have been found by researchers to be important contributors to an entrepreneurial orientation and to be responsible for decision-making towards growth (e.g. Alam et al., 2015; Balog et al., 2014; Ismail, 2016; Kotey & Meredith, 1997; Usman & Mat, 2017). The majority of this research shares a single concept. That is social capital is deemed to be social interaction, which affords information, resources, and support for entrepreneurs.

Social capital can be considered the collection of resources that are provided through having ties to other individuals (Bosma et al., 2016). Social capital is seen as providing an outstanding basis for creating entrepreneurial activities and facilitating the development of competitive advantage (Huang & Wang, 2013; Kaasa, 2009; Chisholm & Nielsen, 2009; Seferiadis, 2016). Social capital is a resource that has been shown to be particularly important for social entrepreneurs (Basu, 2012; Slotte-Kock & Coviello, 2010; Won, Wan & Sharif, 2017).

Several scholars have studied the relationship between social capital and entrepreneurship, and Social capital is considered to promote the perspective of the start-up of entrepreneurship (Li, 2015; Murphy, 2011). In examining this issue, Davidsson and Honig (2003) found that bridging and bonding social capital, with either strong or weak ties, were excellent predictors of who would become a nascent entrepreneur and who would advance through the start-up process. Kreiser, Patel, and Fiet (2013) found that an increase in the strength of network ties was associated negatively with founding activities while an increase in the number of ties was associated positively with founding activities. Mayo, Helms, Becherer, and Finch (2002) examination of the relationship between motivated entrepreneurs and entrepreneurial awareness and found awareness was significantly correlated with a social network, and support and extend this new perspective toward entrepreneurial orientation.

Many other authors (Linan, 2007; Bauernschuster, Falck & Heblich, 2010; Tatarko, 2013; Sharma, 2014; Lee, 2017) have emphasized the positive role of social capital in facilitating entrepreneurship. Among these positive roles are that social capital helps in opportunity identification (Bhagavatula, Elfring, Mair & Marti, 2010; Lechner, Kirschenhofer & Dowling, 2016; Stam, 2010), the establishment of a business (Birley, 2000; Lechner et al., 2016) and achieving other desirable outcomes (Stam, Arzlanian & Elfring, 2014). Theoretically speaking, the influence of entrepreneurial learning on the success of start-up firms has been the subject of previous research (Beek, 2017). The literature often has found a positive relationship between education and entrepreneurship (Burge, 2017; Delmar & Davidsson, 2000; Raposo & Paço, 2011; Rocha, Carneiro & Varum, 2015). Indeed, most research on social entrepreneurship has found a positive relationship. In their review of a 2015 GEM survey that drew upon interviews with 167,793 adults in 58 economies, Bosma, Schutjens and Volker (2016) noted that the social entrepreneurship prevalence rate was higher for educated individuals than for uneducated individuals, and the highest rate was highest among individuals with post-secondary education. Furthermore, Hoogendoorn, van der Zwan and Thurik (2011), Harding and Cowling

(2006), Martín and Cuervo-Arango (2017) and Kachlami (2014) of numerous different countries all demonstrated a positive relationship between education and social entrepreneurship. Furthermore, people with a higher level of education may have a greater probability of achieving success and the fulfillment of their personal goals as entrepreneurs as well as employees (Gimeno et al., 1997; Bosma et al., 2016; McDowall & Micinski, 2010).

In terms of education, Reyes and Manipol (2015) examined how education can help to develop entrepreneurship. In a survey of students, they found that the sharing of the experiences of entrepreneurs with students received the highest positive response rate, and more than half of the respondents strongly agreed that these interactions helped increase the entrepreneurial awareness of students. Second, on the list of proposed activities that could help increase the entrepreneurial awareness of students were visits to companies.

Entrepreneurs seem to have special qualities. According to Burge (2017), Capelleras, Contín-Pilart, Martín-Sánchez, and Larraza-Kintana (2013), Clercq and Arenius (2006) and Fernandes et al. (2017), entrepreneurs have the ability to recognize the correct entrepreneurial opportunities and their ability to perceive good business opportunities has been considered to be their most distinguishing characteristic. Accordingly, individuals who possess greater amounts of knowledge tend to discover more entrepreneurial opportunities, have a more successful entrepreneurial orientation and discover new opportunities (Davidsson & Honig, 2003; Gonzalez-Alvarez & Solis-Rodriguez, 2011; Karimi et al., 2016). Davidsson and Honig (2003) noted that individuals with higher-quality human capital should be better at perceiving these opportunities. Once involved in the entrepreneurial process, these individuals should also exhibit a superior ability to exploit opportunities successfully. On another hand, Baptista et al. (2014), Dimov (2010) and Rauch and Rijdsdijk (2013) said that human capital has a role in developing a new company but does not have a direct effect on the emergence of a new business.

People rarely have total knowledge during selection and decision making. That is because of limitations in their information-storing and information-processing abilities. Thus, knowing other entrepreneurs has been found to be positively and significantly related to being a nascent entrepreneur, and knowing these entrepreneurial others has a positive impact because other entrepreneurs can serve as effective role models (Weber & Milliman, 1997; Arenius & Minniti, 2005).

The majority of the studies have focused on entrepreneurial orientation as a firm level construct and measure the influence of entrepreneurial orientation on firm performance (Pretheeba, 2014). Most studies have been carried out among nascent entrepreneurs who actually work in new business and but have ignored persons who remain in the process of starting a new business (Baporikar, 2015; Phua, 2013). Additionally, the enhancement of entrepreneurial orientation at individual levels has received little attention from researchers (Razavi & Ab Aziz, 2015), especially among youth. To fill this gap, this current study was undertaken to gain a comprehensive picture of social entrepreneurial orientation among Malaysian students toward a new venture.

This study is different from other studies. This study identifies the social entrepreneurial orientation of respondents as a comparison metric with other variables. These variables include entrepreneurial awareness, social capital, and human capital among young adults, which have been proven to play significant roles in the development of emerging economies (Hamid et al., 2017; Yiu, Wan, Ng, Chen & Su, 2014).

A more comprehensive social capital network can impact the career intentions of students who are deciding upon their future careers, particularly with respect to a choice to become an entrepreneur (Sharma, 2014). Cao, Simsek & Jansen (2015); Chia and Liang (2016); Davidsson and Honig (2003) found that bridging social capital can stimulate a person to become an entrepreneur and higher level of entrepreneurial conviction, Linan and Santos (2007) found that social capital plays an essential role in ensuring social relationships, especially for youth (Chia & Liang, 2016), who are particularly critical in developing social ventures to address social problems. Thus, social capital is valuable in establishing a social enterprise and making it successful (Ip et al., 2017). To date; however, only a handful of studies have investigated the role of social capital among

youth, and those studies have generally focused on adolescents (Moinolmolki, 2016; Salehi, 2015; Schaefer-McDaniel, 2004).

Governments and universities must develop of social capital and human capital by creating more entrepreneurial awareness, which is a key driver of an entrepreneurial orientation (Mayo et al., 2002) (Hamid et al., 2017; Yiu et al., 2014). Entrepreneurial awareness provides excellent foundation for developing entrepreneurial activities (Huang & Wang, 2013; Huang, Wang, Tseng & Wang, 2010; Kaasa, 2009; Chisholm & Nielsen, 2009; Seferiadis, 2016), creating an entrepreneurial orientation and discovering new opportunities (Davidsson & Honig, 2003; Gonzalez-Alvarez & Solis-Rodriguez, 2011; Karimi et al., 2016). Along with this vein, many scholars and researchers have stressed that increasing entrepreneurial awareness will lead to business incubation and facilitate students in starting a business venture (Pretheeba, 2014; Yamamoto, 2011).

However, the bulk of extant studies that have examined social capital, human capital, and entrepreneurial awareness gave focused on social entrepreneurship, particularly in developed world (Dzisi & Otsyina, 2014 ; Santos, 2012; Seferiadis, 2016; Veselinova & Parleev, 2017; Schwarz, 2017; Bruton, Ketchen & Ireland, 2013; Madhooshi & Samimi, 2015; Littlewood & Holt, 2018). Accordingly, fewer studies are available on social capital, human capital, and entrepreneurial awareness in developing countries, especially among universities students (Moinolmolki, 2016; Salehi, 2015; Schaefer-McDaniel, 2004; Montiel Campos, 2017; Mamabolo, Kerrin & Kele, 2017). In addition, few studies have been conducted on social entrepreneurship and resilience among the public university students in Malaysia (Ab Wahida et al., 2016).

Based on the above premise, therefore, it is logical to conclude that previous researchers have paid minimal attention to social capital, human capital and entrepreneurial awareness in social entrepreneurial orientation. Thus, many opportunities abound to extend the literature on social capital, human capital, entrepreneurial awareness and social entrepreneurial orientation among students theoretically and empirically. Consequently, the specific objective of this article is to present a conceptual framework that links social capital, human capital and entrepreneurial orientation and will contribute to the body of knowledge.

This remainder of this article is organized as follows. Based on the objective of this study, the second part is a literature review on social capital, human capital, entrepreneurial awareness and social entrepreneurial orientation among students. The next part presents the conceptual framework of the study, which shows the relationship between social capital, human capital, entrepreneurial awareness and social entrepreneurial orientation. And, the last part is the conclusion and suggestions for future research.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Social capital

Social capital can be referred to as an individual's collection of social resources, including social cohesion and social networks (Almedom, 2005; Gedajlovic et al., 2013; Lin & Erickson, 2008; Lin et al., 2014) from which information and resources are obtained (Bolino et al., 2002; Lin & Erickson, 2010). As such, access to the network and social ties are considered a valuable resource for an entrepreneur (Arregle et al., 2015; Singh et al., 1999; Zane, 2011). Examples of social capital include relationships with family, professional club memberships, or civic organization memberships (Poon, Thai, & Naybor, 2012). The social network connections of entrepreneurs provide the social resources to mobilize the financial or intellectual resources needed to identify and exploit rapidly changing business opportunities with the help of social capital (Ming & Zuguang, 2013; Stam et al., 2014; Pease & Cunningham, 2016). The social capital literature suggests that individual social network connections help entrepreneurs to reduce the search costs for locating suppliers and customers (Chuluunbaatar, Ottavia, & Kung, 2011). While making social connections is one way to build social capital, making investments in business is another way to build relationships with entrepreneurs (Burge, 2017).

The relationship of social capital with entrepreneurship has been of academic interest for a long time (Kwon, Heflin & Ruef, 2013). Social capital is seen as being critical to successful entrepreneurship (Gedajlovic et al., 2013) and a central determinant of entrepreneurial outcomes (Smith, Smith & Shaw, 2017). That is because social capital can aid entrepreneurs in realizing opportunities (Hellenes, 2016; Esfandabadi, Farsi, Mobaraki, Esfandabadi, 2016), in acquiring resources (Davidsson & Honig, 2003; Dowla, 2011; Esfandabadi et al., 2016), and in achieving other desirable outcomes (Stam et al., 2014). Thus, such works bolster the notion that the acquisition of social capital serves a key role in the entrepreneurial success of both individuals and collectives. According to Basu (2012), Slotte-Kock and Coviello (2010), and Won, Wan and Sharif (2017) social capital is a resource that is especially vital for social entrepreneurs.

Indeed, social entrepreneurship has been seen to have strong links with social capital (Seferiadis, 2016; Thompson, Mawson & Martin, 2017; Westlund & Larsson, 2016; Mokhtar, Abdullah & Kin, 2014). For example, many studies have been conducted the importance of entrepreneurial networks for business success (Abou-Moghli & Al Muala, 2012; Birley, 1985; Elfring & Hulsink, 2003; Hoang & Antonic, 2003; Johannisson, 2000; Leitch, McMullan & Harrison, 2013; Perera, 2015; Stephens, 2013). In addition, the evidence exists that social capital stimulates the process of social entrepreneurship in developmental contexts (Bhagavatula et al., 2010; Seferiadis, 2016). Social capital portrays mutually beneficial actions and relationships to overcome the challenges (Hitayezu, 2016), and social entrepreneurship is about the dynamics of a win-win situation, as social entrepreneurship joins social issues with economic benefits (Fowler, 2000; Tuli & Gupta, 2018). Hence, social capital might be the best concept to show how social entrepreneurs function (Seferiadis, 2016).

In relationship to this several scholars have examined the relationship between social capital and social entrepreneurship among college students. For example, Jemari et al. (2017) investigated the level of entrepreneurial intention among public university students in Sarawak Malaysia. The findings revealed that social capital had a strong and positive correlation with the social entrepreneurial intention scale. Also, Ndofirepi and Rambe (2016) conducted a quantitative survey among 169 polytechnic college students in Zimbabwe to establish their entrepreneurial orientations. The results partially confirmed that the entrepreneurial orientations of students were directly linked to their opportunity recognition beliefs and their perceived entrepreneurial capabilities. Besides this, some social entrepreneurship literature has suggested that both financial and social capital play key roles in venture start-ups and their success (Mair & Martí, 2006); Littlewood & Holt (2018).

Although several studies have also examined the relationship between social capital and entrepreneurship (Naeiji & Safikhani, 2013) directly, a scarcity of research exists on the relationship between social capital and social entrepreneurial orientation. With the increasing importance of an entrepreneurial orientation, researchers have looked at the influence of social capital on the entrepreneurial orientation of firms (e.g., Rodrigo-Alarcón et al., 2017; Stam & Elfring, 2008). Rarely have these studies investigated the facets of social capital altogether. Even when studies have mentioned entrepreneurial orientation and social capital, they typically have treated them as discrete variables with no discussion of their interrelationships (Liu & Lee, 2015; Stam & Elfring, 2008). However, identifying situations in which interrelationships improve entrepreneurial orientation and entrepreneurial awareness is especially critical, especially among undergraduates. Understanding the experiential phenomena relative to entrepreneurship will allow social entrepreneurship programs, universities, and youth policy makers to better implement a strategy for social entrepreneurship.

In addition, several researchers have examined the association between social capital and social entrepreneurial orientation in developed countries (Seferiadis, 2016; Schwarz, 2017; Madhooshi & Samimi, 2015; Littlewood & Holt, 2018). However, relatively few studies have properly dealt with the interaction of social capital and entrepreneurship in the developing world (Afandi, Kermani & Mammadov, 2016; Gedajlovic et al. 2013; Hoang & Antoncic 2003; Westlund, Larsson & Olsson, 2014). Moreover, Jemari et al. (2017) suggested that future research should consider mediation by arguing that little understanding exists of

the causal mechanisms of how or why social capital affects other variables. And also, they recommended more research to examine what constructs can mediate between social capital and social entrepreneurship. Thus, the following hypotheses are posited for further empirical examination.

H1: Social capital has a significant effect on the social entrepreneurial orientation.

H2: Social capital has a significant effect on entrepreneurial awareness.

2.2 Human capital

Semantically speaking, the term human capital is a combination of human and capital (Harpan & Draghici, 2014; Kwon, 2009). Despite this simplicity, issues concerning the proper definition and measurement of human capital have been debated by scholars for the past few decades (Veselinova & Parleev, 2017). Different perspectives of human capital have been given by previous scholars (Florin et al., 2003; Veselinova & Parleev, 2017). For example, the definition of human capital, according to Becker (1994), includes individual knowledge and skills that create commercial value, which comes from general knowledge and skills or from specific individual skills (Becker, 1994). Or, human capital can be defined as an investment in the talents, experience, skill, knowledge or other intangible assets of individuals an engine for business growth and the main factor in new business formation (Erbasi, 2016; Kunnas, 2016; Quan & Huy, 2014; Schriver, 2017). For the purposes of this study, human capital is understood as an investment in human knowledge, skills and experience to create economic value, relevant for social entrepreneurship.

While research supports the influence of human capital and social capital on entrepreneurship, a closer assessment of this relationship can help in shaping economic policies create jobs through entrepreneurship (Unger, Rauch, Frese & Rosenbusch, 2011; Westlund et al., 2014; Burge, 2017). Capital is vital to those concerned with entrepreneurship (Cetindamar, Gupta, Karadeniz & Egrican, 2012); specifically, this capital includes human capital and the social network connections and the social capital resources of an entrepreneur (Becker, 1994; Schutjens & Völker, 2010). Bacq, Hartog and Hoogendoorn (2016) determined that, in relative terms, the weighting of skills in entrepreneurial human capital is lower for social entrepreneurs than for commercial entrepreneurs, while social entrepreneurs may be superior in general skills. Those skills enable social entrepreneurs to ascertain the nature of positive external effects.

In the literature on social entrepreneurship, most studies have found a positive relationship between education and entrepreneurship. In reviewing the results of a 2015 GEM Bosma et al. (2016) found that the rate of social entrepreneurship was higher among educated individuals, with the highest being highest among individuals with post-secondary education. The studies of Hoogendoorn, van der Zwan, and Thurik (2011), Harding and Cowling (2006), Martín and Cuervo-Arango (2017), and Kachlami (2014) of several different countries found a positive relationship between education and social entrepreneurship. The influence of entrepreneurial learning on the success of start-up firms has had some previous studies. In these studies, it was found that those individuals with a higher level of education may also have a greater probability of achieving success and fulfilling their personal goals as entrepreneurs or as employees (Bosma et al., 2016; Gimeno et al., 1997; McDowall & Micinski, 2010). However, calls have been for additional research on the linkage between human capital and social entrepreneurship (Blackburn & Kovalainen, 2009; Rae & Wang, 2015; Archana & Jaichitra, 2017).

With respect to experience, van der Sluis et al. (2008) and Yaacob, Shaupi and Shuaib (2016) have argued that, in addition to the level of education, the choice of school courses or training programs might be a key determinant of entrepreneurship. They added that little is known in the literature concerning the impacts of specific training on entrepreneurial outcomes. Kim, Aldrich and Keister (2006) and Knatko, Shirokova and Bogatyreva (2016) found that prior entrepreneurial and managerial experience provided a great repertoire of skills necessary to begin a new business. Indeed, the entrepreneurship literature has indicated that nascent entrepreneurs with prior entrepreneurial or managerial experience have more knowledge of the various

activities associated with beginning a firm more young inexperienced entrepreneurs, such as how to develop contacts with customers and financiers, gather and allocate resources, organize internal processes and structures, and attract and retain employees (Davidsson & Honig, 2003; Delmar & Shane 2006; Dimov, 2010; Grichnik et al., 2014, Knatko et al., 2016). Corner and Ho (2010) and Ernst (2018) have indicated that experience in entrepreneurship and in the relevant social field are necessary. Typically, young, nascent entrepreneurs lack both of these sources of useful insights.

Some have studies that mention relevant skills for social entrepreneurship include both entrepreneurial and social entrepreneurship factors. Petit (2018) and Ernst (2018) noted that it was crucial for a social entrepreneur to have socially oriented skills when becoming a change maker in society. Also, numerous previous studies on the origins of social entrepreneurship have mentioned the linkage with knowledge and experience. Indeed, Corner and Ho (2010) and Ernst (2018) have indicated that experience in entrepreneurship and in the relevant social field are necessary.

Building upon these themes, many other works have similarly looked into psychological and sociological influences to examine different causes of entrepreneurial awareness (Fretschner & Weber, 2013; Gaglio & Katz, 2001; Levie, Kelley, Martínez & Schøtt, 2014; Swart, 2014). Gaglio and Katz (2001) argued strongly that differences in mental schema and cognition abilities of individuals help to explain why opportunities are recognized by some and not by others. Similarly, those researchers who embrace the subjectivist perspective have expounded on the belief that the extent of entrepreneurial awareness or alertness is very much driven by an individual's interpretative framework or his/her existing stock of knowledge. This knowledge is derived from life experiences such as everyday encounters, social interactions, crisis management, problem-solving arguments, or adverse changes in the external environment.

Moreover, Pihie and Sani (2009) have explored the entrepreneurial mindset of university students after completing an entrepreneurship education course. They found that the utilization of teaching techniques to infuse entrepreneurial skills and behavior in students had improved the entrepreneurial awareness of students, and the students are able to develop the entrepreneurial skills and behavior necessary for their studies. Apparently, educational work can have a moderate effect on increasing the entrepreneurial awareness and cognition of students (Wu, Wu & Li, 2017). In addition, Chen et al. (2015) pointed out that entrepreneurship education cultivates entrepreneurial awareness, thinking and skills via educational methods. Moreover, Fretschner and Weber (2013) said that entrepreneurship promotion policy measures should begin by stimulating entrepreneurial awareness. In doing so, it should be remembered that age, social experiences, professional knowledge, risk perception and other factors affect students as they think entrepreneurial activities (Shu, 2016).

Numerous studies have revealed a linkage between human capital and entrepreneurship in developed countries (McKague, Wong & Siddiquee, 2017; Veselinova & Parleev, 2017; Sequeira, Gibbs & Juma, 2016; Yamamoto, 2012). Hence, little research has investigated the impact of human capital on entrepreneurship or the social entrepreneurship (Lee, 2017; Unger et al., 2011). In addition, Jemari et al. (2017) recommended adding a mediator to the human capital and student social entrepreneurship relationship. Furthermore, studies have supported the notion that human capital improves social entrepreneurship (Archana & Jaichitra, 2017; Estrin, Mickiewicz & Stephan, 2016; Seferiadis, 2016).

Recent studies have examined the relationship between human capital and social entrepreneurship, but the results have been mixed. Some have found a positive relationship between human capital and social entrepreneurship (Davidsson, 1995; Davidsson & Honig, 2003; Estrin, Mickiewicz & Stephan, 2016; Evans & Leighton, 2002; Gimeno et al., 1997; Reynolds, 1997; Jiao, 2011; Mokhtar, Abdullah & Kin, 2014). According to Iyigun and Owen (1998), Rosenbusch, Rauch, Parker and Unger (2009), Unger et al. (2011), Urban and Kongo (2015) and Bosma et al. (2016) human capital traits such as education, relevant expertise and specific knowledge are critical to social entrepreneurship project success. However, other studies have found a negative relationship (Elert, Andersson & Wennberg, 2015; Bitros & Karayiannis, 2010; Gössling, 2003; Jiménez et al.,

2015). These inconsistent results in the literature necessitate a further investigation of the relationship between human capital and social entrepreneurial orientation, particularly in developing countries where a profound lack of relevant studies exists (Mamabolo et al., 2017). Additionally, calls have been for more research on the linkage between human capital and social entrepreneurship (Wang & Chugh, 2015; Seferiadis, 2016).

As mentioned before, previous studies have revealed positive a relationship between human capital, entrepreneurial awareness and social entrepreneurship (Dzisi & Otsyina, 2014; Jemari et al., 2017; Waghid & Oliver, 2017; Andriyansah & Zahra, 2017). Thus, the following can be hypothesized:

H3: Human capital has a significant effect on the social entrepreneurial orientation.

H4: Human capital has a significant effect on entrepreneurial awareness.

2.3 Entrepreneurial awareness

Kirzner (1973, 2015) employed the expression awareness to describe entrepreneurial identification of opportunity. Brahma and Panda (2014), Ray and Cardozo (1996) and Mayo et al. (2002) said that any identification of opportunity by a potential entrepreneur is heralded by a sensitive awareness to information. In the extant literature, many definitions exist. Some describe entrepreneurial awareness and as an inclination to become aware of and be susceptible to information concerning matter and event. Hall and Matthews (2017) confirmed that action could be conceptualized as the creation of new products, new processes, entry into new markets or the creation of new ventures.

Along the same lines, awareness is seen as the first step in motivating and nurturing individuals towards entrepreneurship (Brownson, 2015). Bridge and O'Neill (2012) said that pursuing entrepreneurship can be equated to selecting an occupation and being successful requires an initial awareness of entrepreneurship. Possibly, everyone is aware that they could be entrepreneurial or that entrepreneurship could offer the potential for them. Thus, the first intervention step in this process may be social persuasion to increase the awareness of entrepreneurship and its potential benefits (Bridge & O'Neill, 2012). Therefore, raising awareness is a crucial step in the nurturing of an entrepreneurial culture (Brownson, 2015; Claire & Perryman, 2016; Xheneti, 2007). If an entrepreneurship orientation is to be attained as such, the entrepreneurship awareness must be stimulated.

Entrepreneurial awareness refers to the individual consciousness tendency that plays an activist role in the entrepreneurial process, individual motives, beliefs, and interests embodied (Jing & Yi-Han, 2017). As a key way to form a sense of entrepreneurial awareness, entrepreneurial awareness education has a positive effect on the cultivation of college students' autonomy, risk consciousness and cooperation consciousness, so as to promote the enhancement the learning behavior and enhance the self-quality of college students. Fretschner and Weber (2013) said that the decision of a student to become an entrepreneur was heavily dependent on a personal attitude component.

At the same time, strengthening the cultivation of entrepreneurial awareness can effectively improve the foundation of student entrepreneurship and promote employment by entrepreneurship (Jing & Yi-Han, 2017). Pretheeba (2014) argued that the success of a new venture depends on the effective utilization of resources and supports provided by the government and other institutions. And, he noted that increasing awareness about the resources available through numerous institutions facilitates students in starting a business venture more easily. Robertson and Collins (2003) said that by learning, and connecting with the business community and assisting in the assessment and creation of course material students are helping to create best practices both for themselves and for the university.

Numerous studies have revealed the relationship between entrepreneurial awareness and social entrepreneurship in developed countries (e.g., Ashton, Ross & Beyers, 2006; Chikumbo, Öztürk & Tate, 2012). Conversely, little research has investigated the impact of entrepreneurial awareness in social entrepreneurship in developing countries (Shrestha, 2013). In addition, Jemari et al. (2017) recommended the inclusion of the

mediator to the social entrepreneurship relationship. According to Montiel Campos (2017) and Mamabolo et al. (2017), a research gap exists of entrepreneurial awareness as a mediated variable.

Furthermore, studies have supported the notion that awareness leads to improved social entrepreneurship (Andriyansah & Zahra, 2017; Türker, Özerim & Yildiz, 2017; Hendrikse, 2014). Related to that, as a key way to form a sense of entrepreneurial awareness, entrepreneurial awareness education has a positive effect on the cultivation of college students' autonomy, risk consciousness, and cooperation consciousness, so as to promote the enhancement of college students' learning behavior. At the same time, strengthening the cultivation of entrepreneurial awareness can improve the foundation of student entrepreneurship and promote employment by entrepreneurship (Jing & Yi-Han, 2017). Pretheeba (2014) argued that the success of a new venture depends on the effective utilization of resources and support provided by the government and other institutions. And, he noted that increasing the awareness about the resources available through numerous institutions facilitates students in beginning a business venture more easily. Therefore, NGOs, universities and governments should embrace awareness activities as a strategy to build entrepreneurial awareness to improve the capabilities of students and their entrepreneurship activities with the purpose of orienting towards social entrepreneurship (Spear et al., 2012; Hendrikse, 2014; Nawi et al., 2018; Dzisi & Otsyina, 2014). This discussion leads to the following hypotheses:

H5: Entrepreneurial awareness has a significant influence on social entrepreneurial orientation.

H6: Entrepreneurial awareness significantly mediates the relationship between social capital and social entrepreneurial orientation.

H7: Entrepreneurial awareness significantly mediates the relationship between human capital and social entrepreneurial orientation.

2.4 Social entrepreneurial orientation

Entrepreneurial orientation has been an area of increased research attention in recent years (Alam et al., 2015; Arbaugh, Cox & Camp, 2009; Martens et al., 2016; Rauch, Wiklund et al., 2009) and has become an important construct in entrepreneurial studies (Rauch et al., 2009). Miller (1983) introduced the original framework of entrepreneurial orientation using the dimensions of innovation, proactiveness, and risk-taking to measure entrepreneurship. Several subsequent studies adopted these three dimensions (Cong, Dempsey & Xie, 2017; Covin & Lumpkin, 2011; Covin & Slevin, 1989; Deb & Wiklund, 2017; Rainwater, 2016; Xing & Wang, 2014).

A major change in the view of entrepreneurship occurred in the mid-1990s with a transition away from entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial orientation being studied in companies towards the study of entrepreneurial orientation in individuals. According to Ndofirepi and Rambe (2016), if small businesses operations can be considered as the outcomes of an entrepreneur's decisions, then arguing that manifestations of entrepreneurial orientation at the organizational levels denote the activities of an individual is logical. Lumpkin and Dess (1996) theorized that an entrepreneurial orientation existed in individuals related to the actual processes and activities in which people engage to formulate and introduce a new business venture. These researchers used the dimensions of proactiveness, innovativeness, and risk-taking of an entrepreneurial orientation that others had already put forth (Saric, 2012).

According to Ndofirepi and Rambe (2016), entrepreneurship orientation strategies exhibit at the levels of organizations are just expressions and extensions of individual entrepreneurial behaviors. This because organizations are a culmination of the regulatory rules, administrative, activities, and arrangements that individuals set forth. Hence, the willingness of an entrepreneur to assume risks and be proactive in leading his/her organization can be key behaviours that an individual (e.g., a student) may take on in other life activities.

Bolton & Lane (2012) and Robinson & Stubberud (2014) show that Individuals, like students, can easily be observed as innovative or not innovative or as either risk takers or non-risk takers.

The social orientation of an entrepreneur depends on individual characteristics related to his/her personality (Sastre-Castillo et al., 2015). According to Williams and Nadin (2012), social entrepreneurs provide individualist or social reasons for their activities. Individualist reasons encompass the wish to work more job autonomy, to not have a boss, more career freedom and less pressure, or to have a new occupation after retirement to promote their positions on society. Among the social reasons are helping other people, provide solutions to issues such as health, education, housing, or improving the environment and community support of some kind. Other authors also have highlighted certain traits about the leadership and organisational skills that are characteristic of social entrepreneurs (Dhesi, 2010; Johnson, 2004; Sastre-Castillo et al., 2015; Shaw, & Carter, 2007; Ülgen, 2019).

Several researchers have proposed the measurement of social entrepreneurship orientation. Kraus et al. (2017), in their study of factors driving or influencing social entrepreneurial orientation, noted that risk-taking, innovativeness, and pro-activeness were among the key constructs that determine and drive an individual's entrepreneurial orientation. Covin and Slevin (1989) developed these into an instrument to measure the entrepreneurial orientation of organizations, and these behaviours have been used to measure entrepreneurial orientation at an academic level and high school (e.g., Rainwater, 2016; Taatila & Down, 2012; Salgado, 2016; Kraus et al., 2017; Kudonoo & Nkansah, 2018 & Kurniawan et al., 2019 Bolton and Lane (2012) developed an instrument to measure the entrepreneurial orientation of university students, that identified traits of individuals in areas of innovativeness, proactivity, and risk taking, which was found to relate with entrepreneurial orientation. Salgado (2016) examined the reliability and validity of these measures, and on the computation of an overall entrepreneurial orientation outcome.

According to Abu-Saifan (2012), despite the fact that there has been growth in the utilization of the term social entrepreneur, the field to which it refers has not matured yet when compared to the research on entrepreneurship as a whole. Researchers are still attempting to create legitimacy regarding the term by describing the success of people in social entrepreneurship. Based on the general outlook of research towards social entrepreneurship, Abu-Saifan (2012) found that the research on social entrepreneurship fell short when compared to other fields of entrepreneurship. He also noted a need for more studies that explored the different constructs of social entrepreneurship and increased the general understanding of the topic.

Overall, based on the foregoing, the review of the literature has identified a theoretical gap that needs to be filled as demonstrated in the conceptual model. Specifically, it has been established in the literature that several constructs are linked with a social entrepreneurial orientation. First, social capital and human capital have an effect on social entrepreneurial orientation. Some literature has reported a positive link between the variables while others have reported a negative result. Therefore, these mixed results constitute the very reason for this paper to further explain the relationship among and between social capital, human capital, and social entrepreneurial orientation. Additionally, the paper introduces entrepreneurial awareness as mediating variable to further, strengthen the said relationships.

Also of note is that the variables that will be examined in this study have not been explored in the context of social entrepreneurship. Thus, this research contains a unique contribution to the field of social entrepreneurship, which has received little attention so far.

3. Conceptual Model

Based on the reviewed literature and subsequently suggested hypotheses, the following conceptual model was developed to explain the relationship between the variables of the study.

Figure 3.1. Research Framework

A thorough review of the literature reveals that the effects of social capital and human capital on social entrepreneurial orientation have been found to be inconsistent. To solve this type of inconsistency instance, this study suggests that the entrepreneurial awareness are likely to serve as important mediators of these relationships, and could help to illustrate the mechanism through which this influence could be made effective. The proposed framework could provide guidelines for empirical research designed to explore the determinants of social entrepreneurial orientation among students especially in the context of the current technological revolution and globalization.

Also, entrepreneurial awareness as a variable might increase the influence of social entrepreneurial orientation. Furthermore, support of entrepreneurial awareness affects the successful implementation of social entrepreneurship in general. Therefore, this paper is unique in the sense that, for the first time, it has within the context of the literature provided a logical model that will help governments, universities, and NGOs develop programs and activities that raise social entrepreneurial awareness among students as guided by the previous studies and theories.

To formulate a holistic social entrepreneurship framework, combining the most ambitious of all possible ideas, and to think about what the most relevant factors or dimensions are to be included in the framework is necessary. This study combined the ideas and factors to explain the factors that influenced social entrepreneurship orientation from established social theories, and proposed a new framework.

In addition, this study proposed a new framework incorporating three theories from diverse disciplines to form the theoretical foundation for this study. The three theories used included: the Social Capital Theory (Coleman, 1990 & Putnam, 1993), the Entrepreneurial Orientation Theory (Miller, 1983; Covin & Slevin, 1989; Covin, Lumpkin, 2011), and the Human Capital Theory (Becker, 1964).

4. Conclusion

Building on previous knowledge, this paper sought to expand discussion about the social entrepreneurship among undergraduate students by investigating the relationship between social capital, human capital, entrepreneurial awareness, and social entrepreneurial orientation. In this paper show that it is possible to present three theorems (the Social Capital Theory, the Entrepreneurial Orientation Theory, and the Human Capital Theory), from some general common ideas. Indeed, this paper set a very useful and unique theoretical framework, that could be a reference model to search the orientation of students towards social entrepreneurship and which variables can influence this orientation. This study has provided a research framework that links the relationship among and between social capital, human capital, entrepreneurial awareness, and social entrepreneurial orientation. Importantly, this study makes an important contribution to the body of knowledge by providing a framework that allows for an explanation of the influence of social capital, and human capital on social entrepreneurial orientation. Moreover, this study is unique as it elucidates the possibilities of using entrepreneurial awareness as a mediator in the relationship among social capital, human capital, and social entrepreneurial orientation.

The principal contribution of this paper is the introduction of entrepreneurial awareness as mediator. If social entrepreneurship is to be impactful and dynamic, and a discernable topical area, then employing research to determine whether the approach is successful is critical and if the approach is successful, it will be useful for

researchers and practitioners alike to understand the approach that supports about long term success. Researchers also need to understand better the constraints, support and contextual factors that relate to more effective and less effective enterprises. The opportunity to understand the workability of this research framework should be studied and verified using empirical data in the context of a social entrepreneurship agenda either in Malaysia or elsewhere in the world.

5. References

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